

effects of Climatic extremes On eCOsystem Stability

COCOS

Data Management Plan

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Project

effects of Climatic extremes On eCOsystem Stability

Acronym: COCOS

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Abstract

Ecosystems provide many key services essential for our wellbeing. These services depend on the temporal stability of plant communities. In turn, stability depends on resistance, which is the capacity of plant communities to withstand exogenous perturbations, and on recovery from their impact. Extreme climatic events disrupt the stability of ecosystems, with unpredictable consequences on ecosystem services. As the intensity and frequency of climatic extremes is expected to rise, understanding how ecosystems respond to extremes is an extremely urgent task. Previous studies exploring the stability-climatic extremes relationship suffer from different limitations: i) lack of in-situ data on vegetation stability to conduct worldwide analyses; ii) scarce focus on the joint influence of taxonomic and functional diversity in affecting stability mechanisms under extreme climate. Moreover, few investigated if extremes cause critical transitions of ecosystem functions. This has prevented understanding of how different ecosystems react to climatic extremes. This project aims at addressing these limitations and improving our fragmented knowledge on the relationship between extremes and stability. Combining cutting-edge analytical tools with extensive, and novel, global databases of time-series of in-situ vegetation and climatic extremes data, the project will analyse the relationship between stability and climatic anomalies, and how it varies in different ecosystems. Results will provide worldwide predictions of ecosystem-specific resistance and recovery to climatic extremes, and new approaches for anticipating critical transitions of ecosystem functions. These outputs will be essential for i) guiding future policies aimed at reducing the impact of extremes on society; ii) mitigating economic loss due to extremes in crucial sectors such as agriculture and food production; iii) providing new methods for investigating how climatic extremes affect ecosystem services.

1. Data Summary

Datasets used in COCOS

Within COCOS, I will use the following (existing) datasets: **LOTVS**, **HadEX3**, **TRY**, **GRoot**, **ERA-5 Land**. Detailed information on each of these datasets, along with an explanation of their relevance for the project, follow (note that the datasets are listed according to their importance for COCOS):

- **LOTVS - LOnG-Term Vegetation Sampling** (<https://lotvs.csic.es>)

Custodian of this dataset: Francesco de Bello (francesco.bello@ext.uv.es).

LOTVS is provided in Text Format (txt), so I will be able to use it without any conversion. I will use LOTVS version 2, and if a new version becomes available during the project, I will stay with the old version. I will use LOTVS time-series of plant biomass and cover data to compute measures of ecosystem resistance and recovery to climatic extremes. Also, I will use these data to compute different measures of plant community diversity (e.g., species richness).

- **HadEX3** (<https://www.climdex.org/access/>)

Owner of this dataset: Robert Dunn (robert.dunn@metoffice.gov.uk).

HadEX3 can be used in the provided format (netCFD), so it does not need to be converted to other data formats. I will use HadEX3 version 3.0.4. As for LOTVS, if a new version of HadEX3 becomes available during the project, I will stay with the old version. HadEX3 will provide key data for COCOS, as I will use this dataset to obtain temperature- and precipitation-related indices of climatic extremes for the geographic locations for which I have vegetation data (from LOTVS).

- **TRY - the Plant Trait Database** (<https://www.try-db.org/TryWeb/Home.php>)

Owner of this dataset: Jens Kattge (jkattge@bgc-jena.mpg.de) Gerhard Boenisch (boenisch@bgc-jena.mpg.de).

I will be able to use TRY data in the provided format (Text Format - txt), so no conversion is needed for their use. I will use TRY version 6 and I will stay with this version during the project. Using TRY data, I will compute indices of plant community functional diversity and dominant functional strategy (i.e., community weighted means), which will constitute key measures to assess whether and how biodiversity supports the resistance and recovery of ecosystem functions under climatic extremes.

- **Global Root Trait (GRoot) Database** (<https://groot-database.github.io/GRoot/>)

Owner of this dataset: Nathaly Guerrero-Ramírez (kirana1015@gmail.com).

GRooT is provided as a Comma Separated Values (csv) file, so I will be able to use it without any further conversion. Within COCOS, GRooT will serve a similar purpose than TRY, as I will use it to compute indices of below-ground functional diversity and dominant functional strategy (i.e., community weighted means).

- **ERA-5 Land** (<https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.e2161bac>)

Owner of this dataset: European Union, represented by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).

The dataset can be used in the provided format (netCDF) without any conversion needed. I will use ERA-5 Land variables to obtain temperature- and precipitation-related indices of climatic extremes for the geographic locations for which I have vegetation data (from LOTVS). ERA-5 Land variables have finer spatiotemporal resolution (hourly value for 83 climatic parameters at ~ 9 km spatial resolution at the Equator) than HadEX3 data. So, ERA-5 Land will allow me to derive information on climatic extremes that (potentially) better matches the ecological processes investigated within COCOS. However, while HadEX3 provides readily available indices of climatic extremes, ERA-5 Land variables need to be processed to quantify climatic anomalies.

I will keep a copy of all datasets used in the analyses, and I will make it openly available to replicate results derived from COCOS (see section 2 for more details).

Data formats and types

The datasets that I will use or generate within COCOS have the following data formats: netCDF, RData, Comma-separated values, Text format. These are all standardized formats, which allow for interoperability and are suitable for long-term archiving. Detailed information on the data formats used in COCOS, as well as on their link with specific datasets used in the project, follows:

- **netCDF**

This is a standardized format used to store and share large spatiotemporal raster layers. Both HadEX3 and ERA-5 Land data are made available in this format. I will import and process netCDF data in R (R Core Team, 2021) by using specific libraries built to handle spatial data (e.g., *terra*, Hijmans, 2021).

- **RData**

This format is commonly used for storing and sharing data that are imported, processed and/or created in an R environment. I will use RData as an additional data format to share datasets and allow replicating results obtained within COCOS.

- **Comma-separated Values**

This is a standardized format to store data organized as matrix-like objects. For instance, GRooT data are made available in a comma-separated values file. I will import and process comma-separated values files in an R environment (e.g., for filtering and/or join datasets). Also, I will create comma-separated values files to store matrix-like objects (e.g., matrices used for statistical analyses) generated during COCOS.

- **Text format**

Similar to comma-separated values files, Text format files are standardized formats commonly used to store matrix-like objects. LOTVS and TRY data are made available in this format. I will import and process Text format files in R using the `data.table` package (Dowle & Srinivasan, 2021). This R package includes the `fread` function, which simplifies importing Text format files generated with different encodings.

2. FAIR Data

COCOS is fully committed to FAIR principles. In this regard, I planned several actions aimed at maximizing findability, accessibility, interoperability and reproducibility of data and results that I will generate during COCOS.

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Data archived during COCOS will be associated with a persistent digital object identifier (DOI), so that they can be unambiguously identified. Also, data files will be given intuitive names to improve their findability. As an example, I will name the layer reporting the number of days with precipitation above the 95th percentile of the reference period as “precip_95prc”.

Archived data will be associated with rich metadata (in Text or pdf format), which will provide information on how to import and (re)use different data files (e.g., matrix-like objects stored in RData or Text format). I will make metadata publicly and openly available.

I will follow specific standards to organize the metadata and their content. For example, I will intuitively name metadata (e.g., Importing_IndicesClimaticExtremes), so that it will be easy to relate them with the associated data files. Also, I will use headings reporting the full name, affiliation and contact (e-mail) of the author of the metadata, as well as additional information including the date on which the metadata were created and the data files to which the metadata refer to. In the body of the metadata, I will: (i) describe the data files associated with the metadata; (ii) add definitions on the content of the data files (e.g., brief description of the measures/variables included in matrix-like objects, e.g. whether they are integer-, float- and/or string-valued); (iii) provide the version of the R (or other software) libraries used to process the data; (iv) report information on data files property and licensing (see section 2.2 for data property and licensing).

To compile metadata, I will consistently use data dictionaries (e.g., using acronyms such as ‘m’ or ‘d’ for indicating whether climatic data are aggregated over months or days, respectively). Also, I will use search keywords to simplify crossing information on different data files across metadata.

I will make metadata available in a form that can be harvested and indexed. In this regard, in case I modify the content of metadata, I will update their date of creation accordingly (by updating the metadata title and their headings). This way, metadata will be versioned and kept up-to-date.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository

I will release data and associated metadata in Zenodo repositories, while scripts (or other artifacts) will be released through my personal [GitHub](https://github.com/ManueleBazzichetto) (<https://github.com/ManueleBazzichetto>). Both Zenodo and GitHub are safe and trusted

repositories. Zenodo is built and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE project, the latter being funded by the European Commission (find more at <https://zenodo.org>). GitHub is one of the largest Internet hosting services for software development. In my GitHub repositories, I will include a README file, which I will use to provide additional information on where to find metadata and associated data files.

Both Zenodo and GitHub provide versioning of archived data and scripts. Zenodo links archived data to a unique DOI, while GitHub, which is based on the git distributed version control system, automatically tracks changes and updates of scripts and software made during their development. Importantly, GitHub repositories can be linked to Zenodo, which guarantees a long-term archiving of scripts and software. Also, GitHub repositories linked to Zenodo are given a persistent DOI.

Data

All datasets used in COCOS are open and publicly available under CC-BY license, except LOTVS (see Box1 for a summary on data release and re-use conditions). LOTVS gathers time-series of vegetation data from multiple data owners. About 65% of time-series in LOTVS are openly available. The accessibility of the remaining data is either partially restricted (i.e., data are released if data owners do not respond in due time to a data request) or fully restricted (i.e., data are released exclusively after data owners' approval) (for more details, see Sperandii et al. 2021). Data owners of partially or fully restricted time-series data must be offered co-authorship in case of scientific publication. For COCOS, I have (full) access to LOTVS data. Permission was granted by the LOTVS steering committee, which is the entity handling data requests, before the project started.

Data produced within COCOS will not be subject to embargo and will be made immediately open. Also, they will be available after the end of the project, as all repositories used within COCOS allow for long-term data archiving. No 'data access committee' will be required to regulate COCOS-related data requests. Data will be stored in open and fully accessible Zenodo repositories, which are public without restrictions. Scripts and artifacts, e.g. workflows for importing and processing data used and/or generated during COCOS, will be made available on my personal [GitHub](#). Specifically, I will set public GitHub repositories, which are accessible without restrictions. New data produced within COCOS, including those derived from LOTVS (e.g. matrix-like objects including measures of resistance and recovery), will be made publicly available either as RData or as Text format files through Zenodo or my personal [GitHub](#). For reproducibility, in the metadata associated with these RData (or Text Format files), I will refer to the original LOTVS time-series data used in the analyses. In scientific publications and research reports, I will always provide a 'data availability statement' to improve findability and accessibility of data and/or scripts.

Concerning the property of data generated within COCOS, me and the Hosting Institution established the following agreement: The Hosting Institution is the owner of data and other artifacts (e.g., software, scripts) generated within COCOS. I will make data and artifacts openly available through dedicated repositories on Zenodo (for data) and my personal [GitHub](#) (for scripts). I will always indicate that results from COCOS are a property of the Hosting Institution, and I will specify that data will be released under the latest available

version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC-BY). Metadata will be made open under Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication License (CC-0).

Box 1. Summary of conditions for (re)using datasets involved in COCOS.

- **LOTVS - Long-Term Vegetation Sampling** – data available under specific restrictions. LOTVS data are made available upon request. For COCOS, I have already granted permission to download, process and use LOTVS data. I will offer co-authorship to data owners who contributed with their data to COCOS.
- **HadEX3** – freely available with obligation to quote the source (e.g. CC-BY).
- **TRY - the Plant Trait Database** – freely available with obligation to quote the source (e.g. CC-BY).
- **Global Root Trait (GRoot) Database** – freely available with obligation to quote the source (e.g. CC-BY).
- **ERA-5 Land** – freely available with obligation to quote the source (e.g. CC-BY).

2.3. Making data interoperable

All data formats used within COCOS (see section 1), except for RData, can be imported and re-used in several software (e.g., R, Python). Raster layers in netCDF format can be imported and processed in basically all Geographic Information Systems, including open-source software such as QGIS (QGIS.org, 2022). Comma-separated Values and Text format are also widely used in my field of research. RData are specific to the R environment, which may limit their usage. However, R is nowadays among the most widely used open-source software for data analysis in my research community.

New data generated within COCOS (e.g., spatial raster layers or matrix-like objects) will be produced using the same data formats mentioned above and in the “*Data formats and types*” paragraph.

3. Allocation of resources

No resources will be needed for making data and research outputs FAIR. Indeed, none of the repositories that I will use to archive data files and artifacts charge for their services.

I will be responsible for: (i) reviewing, enhancing, cleaning, or standardizing metadata; (ii) finding, gathering, and collecting data; (iii) maintaining the finished resource; (iv) regularly updating this data management plan.

To execute this data management plan, no additional specialist expertise is required. Also, I do not require any hardware or software in addition to what is usually available in the institute.

4. Data security

The possible impact to the project if information is lost, leaked or vandalized is small.

Data generated within COCOS will be stored in safe repositories (Zenodo and GitHub), both having the highest standards in terms of data security. Zenodo servers are managed according to the CERN Security Baseline for Servers (read more at: <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>). GitHub's Information Security Management System has been certified against ISO/IEC 27001:2013 standards (read more at: <https://github.com/security>).

5. Ethics

I will not collect or (re)use 'personal data' that may infringe privacy rights. Data used and/or generated within COCOS are not linked to personal information such as gender identity, religion or health. In any case, I will not use data that allow unambiguously identify individuals.

References

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Sperandii, M. G., De Bello, F., Valencia, E., Götzenberger, L., Bazzichetto, M., Galland, T., ... & Lepš, J. (2022). LOTVS: A global collection of permanent vegetation plots. *Journal of Vegetation Science*, 33(2), e13115. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jvs.13115>

I used the [Data Stewardship Wizard](https://czu.ds-wizard.org) with its *Common DSW Knowledge Model* (ID: dsw:root:2.4.4) knowledge model to produce this DMP. More specifically, I used the <https://czu.ds-wizard.org> DSW instance, where the project has direct URL: <https://czu.ds-wizard.org/projects/0c58031e-6b00-4cb0-8d81-5a70f41db79a>.